

Evaluating the Impact of Role Stress on Work-Family Conflict among the Employees in Organizations

(AUTHOR-1)

Pragalbh Sharma

Research Scholar (Management)
Bundelkhand University, Jhansi (UP)

(AUTHOR-2)

Prof. Aparna Raj

Former Dean and Professor,
Institute of Tourism and Hotel Management
Bundelkhand University, Jhansi (UP)

Abstract

This study has been undertaken by the investigator with a motive to identify the role stress and the different sources of role stress as well as the impact of work-family conflict among the employees working in the organizations. According to Armstrong et al. in (2015) [1], the role stress is described as the tension and conflict which arises due to the roles which are undertaken by a person at any point of time. This has taken place due to a variety of contributing factors working behind that gives birth to the stress like huge changes in the structure of families, sudden and significant increase in the dual earning families, families with single parent, huge change in the family priorities and orientation, increased participation of women at work, and despite of all this, a huge desire of maintaining a work life balance i.e., a balance between the organizational and family roles and responsibilities. This study reveals that the one very prominent and noticeable source of factors causing stress among the employees working in an organization is the Role-Overload. The organizational employees are stressed intensively due to the inter role distance and self role distance as well.

Keywords: teaching professionals, stress, work family conflict, role overload

Introduction

Stress is considered to be an adaptive response towards any intemperate psychological or physiological demand to a person working at any place. It can be caused by so many reasons and many factors are responsible behind the stressful condition of a person which broadly includes pressure for the task fulfillment demands, physical demands, role demands and the major important the interpersonal demands in addition to this Life changes and the life trauma classified as life stressors. But considering all this, it is clearly visible and evident that stress has an

influential role on all of us in the society. So the question arises that if it does have impact on us then what are the measures we can adopt to eliminate the stressors of modern work life. Argumentative intent, demands, when the outcome is important but still it is uncertain are the results of stress at work place. Robbins and Sanghi (2006) [2].

After evaluating all the aspects the study majorly focuses on the role stress of the employees working in the organizations. The role of an employee in an organization is a position assigned in organization set up, in which the expectation of the concerned group people is defined by the organization. To understand the work family conflict and consequences of stress the model proposed by Rotondo et al. (2003) [3], was contributed and accepted widely but it doesn't explain the issues related to work and non work related consequences which was actually a task for constructor to understand the concept. Role stress theory is a key to understand the work family research, but the spotlight focused on the work family interaction which is seems to be the negative side.

1. Figure: Theoretical Framework

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

Source: [https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Muhammadi Sabra Nadeem, Qaisar Abbas, Published 2009 \(Economics\)](https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Muhammadi+Sabra+Nadeem,+Qaisar+Abbas)

Based on the theoretical framework as proposed by Muhammadi Sabra Nadeem and Dr. Qaisar Abbas (2009) [4], in their study to find out the impact of work life conflict on job satisfaction of the employees, it is very evidently described that the work-family conflict or vice versa, Stress (Family related and Work related), Workload (including working hours and job type and job autonomy are all the factors which leads to job satisfaction if they are managed positively and if they remain unmanaged or unnoticed then these factors becomes the contributing factors leading to job dissatisfaction and role stress.

Therefore, it is very much clear that the Work-family conflict and its reciprocal Family-work conflict both may lead to role stress for an individual resulting into dissatisfaction and several severe imbalances in an individual's life due to which neither he is able to manage his role towards his family nor he is able to manage his organizational duties and what is expected out of him as an employee being at a specific position in an organization.

1.1 Organisational Role Stress (ORS)

When the anticipated outcome is significant and doubtful in this case, the stress results from challenging an opportunity and demand as stated by Robbins (2000) [5]. The organizational role stress is developed whenever there is an imbalance amidst an employee or the environment surrounding him or if there is no ability to cope up with the limitations or the demand that is being created.

According to Heller & Watson (2005) [6], the stress is a state in which an employee is provided with a chance in relation to his perceived desires and for which the output is seen as important but uncertain as well. A huge level of stress that remain unnoticed and unmanaged for a long duration of time leads to the decline in the quality, productivity, skills and creativity of the employees and also affects his physical and mental health as well. According to Pareek (2002) [7], the concept of role and the role system have been developed that leads to potential conflicts and stressful situations in future. These various conflicts and stressful situations may take the following forms as discussed hereunder:

- i. **Self Role Distance:** This type of stress is developed due to the conflict amidst the self concept and role expectations of an individual employee from his role as perceived by him. This means that if an employee feels that his role is having a confrontation with his self concept then he start feeling stressed.
- ii. **Inter-Role Distance:** This situation arises when an individual occupies various roles which also leads to multiple demands at a time due to which there are several conflicts amidst the different roles itself which is very common and also highly frequent in this modern society that leads to this type of inter-role distance.
- iii. **Role Ambiguity:** This situation arises when an individual is unknown about the different expectations people have from his role in the organization and in the family as well. This situation may arise due the lack of understanding of the role by the employee or lack of proper communication from the people concerned. Commonly the concept of role ambiguity has been found to be associated with the roles which have been newly created or developed that lack proper communication or understanding as well.
- iv. **Role Expectation Conflict:** This situation arises when there arises multiple confronting expectations from the people who have assigned a role to the individual. This may be from the side of superiors, subordinates, peers etc. which may also lead to an individual role stress.
- v. **Role Overload:** This situation is created when an employee feels overloaded due to too many expectations created by the role sender from the employee or the individual. This may take place due to various reasons, like high expectations, conflicting roles, lack of support from others, lack of power etc.

- vi. **Personal Inadequacy:** Role stress due to personal adequacy arises when an employee feels that he is not fit for a particular job in terms of not having the required capabilities, skills, creativity or training to assume that role properly and hence become ineffective and inefficient to perform that role which gives rise to stress in them.
- vii. **Resource Inadequacy:** This condition is developed when despite of having all the necessary skill set, qualification, training or capabilities too, an employee is not able to perform his duties due to lack of the resources required by an individual to perform his job efficiently.

1.2 Work-Family Conflict (WFC)

This is assumed as a win-lose situation of an individual between the work and one's family. This concept is based on the assumption that the individuals have very limited resources physical and materialistic including time as well that can be allocated sufficiently to the many conflicting and divergent roles which are played by an individual at the workplace and in the family too.

According to Dierdorff et al. (2008) [8], the work family conflict has been described as a type of conflict between the intersecting roles arising out of the work and family of an individual in which the pressure of role performance from both the family and the workplace are highly incompatible up to an extent. Earlier this concept of WFC was observed as a 1-dimensional construct where the researchers suggested that the conflict amidst family and work can only take place at either of the side. But, now this reciprocal relationship between the work-family conflicts has been established and commonly recognized as well.

Discussion

Based on the extensive literature review done by the investigator don this field, some common points of discussion have been brought out. Several research studies have shown a negative correlation in between the two variables: work-family conflict (WFC) and Job satisfaction. This means that the higher level of work-family conflict results into low level of job satisfaction. Perrewe et al. (1999) [9], had explained this negative correlation in their research work as well. Along with they also found that the married females used to experience more stress due to work overload as compared to the unmarried females. Lu et al. (2011) [10], stated that higher amount of workload results into high level of work family conflict among women. Results of this study also explains that majority of the respondents were the working pair where the majority was also found to be concentrated into the Information Technology sector and therefore, they were not able to spare time for their family and children which gave rise to the work family conflict in them leading to disturbance in their work-life. This study also revealed that the peers are more supportive at work as compared to one's own husband or wife that helps in getting job satisfaction up to an extent. Salary has also been found as a predictor of job satisfaction up to an extent that means as the salary increases, job satisfaction also increases. The work to family conflict and vice versa is also related to the working hours. According to Spector et al. (2004) [11], the study resulted that the working hours had a very deep impact over the work family conflict. Despite of the companies offering off shore assignments to their employees, most of the

employees do not find it comfortable and do not accept the offer due to their commitment. The inter-role distance between the employees is due to the work family conflict and vice versa as well as the conflicts amidst the organizational and non-organizational objectives are due to the changed marital status of the employees. There are also concepts like role erosion and resource inadequacy which are also considered as dominant stressors. Role ambiguity and role expectation conflicts found to be contributing to stress at a lesser rate. It is also found that there are some role stressors which are positively related to age, experience, marital status and qualification of the employees.

Conclusion

In order to overcome the problem of role stress and thereby for increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of the individuals while balancing amidst the Work and Family, the following points have been suggested and concluded as a part of this study:

- i.** There should be an appointment of right number of people in an organization to carry out the different roles based on their skill set and specialization.
- ii.** The delegation of a right job to a right person should be done very carefully and that too should be based on the person's efficiency and effectiveness so that the role stress occurring due to role overload can be reduced or eliminated.
- iii.** The policy for promotion and appraisal should be made very fair and transparent and both the promotions and performance appraisal should be done properly at regular time intervals.
- iv.** There should be a proper system of induction or orientation for all the newly joined employees in the organization so that they should be known about their roles, responsibilities and scope of operations related to their job along with explaining the procedure established for the accomplishment of all the tasks related to a particular position so that the role ambiguity may be eliminated.
- v.** Special audits should also be conducted by the management periodically to figure out the various stressors related to the job which can lead to role stress for the employee, which can be easily judged by the low level performance of the employees as compared to the expectations from an individual or a position.
- vi.** The management should also think of organizing the stress management programs, workshops and exercises after regular intervals for the employees for helping them to cope up with the occupational stress and concentrate back to their work.
- vii.** A support system may also be developed by the management of the organization where social support may be provided by the seniors, supervisors, managers, administrators, colleagues, subordinates and by the family itself for making the individual feel comfortable and adjust into the situation, it can also be done by providing personal accomplishments to the individuals.
- viii.** Employees should also be allowed to get involved or participate in day to day problem solving and organization decision making, making them feel as a valued member of the

organization and also making them aware about the different roles and related responsibilities so that they should not feel stressed specifically for their role in the organization.

- ix. The inter-role distance should be managed cautiously so that the conflict between self concept and others expectations and the role perceived by the employee should be justified.
- x. Employees should be dealt humanly and the superiors should closely watch the performance of their subordinates, any unusual change in the behavior or performance of the employees should be taken into consideration and discovered to know if the underlying cause of this change is stress or anything else.

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